

SUSTAINABLE BIOCOMPOSITES FROM A SUPER TOUGHENED NANO-BLEND MATRIX FOR INDUSTRIAL APPLICATIONS

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Keywords: Super-toughened, blends, biocomposites

ABSTRACT

Sustainable bio-composites with filler contents up to 20 wt%, based on our super-toughened polybutylene succinate/ polybutylene adipate terephthalate (PBS/PBAT) nano-blends, were successfully prepared. Different kinds of fillers were used in this research, including miscanthus fiber, oat hull and mineral talc. The influence of different fillers on the mechanical and thermal properties were evaluated; primarily, the effect on the toughness, melt flow index (MFI) and crystallinity brought by the agro-residues fillers were studied and compared to widely used talc. The nano structures of the PBS/PBAT blends were certified by atomic force microscopy (AFM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) technologies, and the dispersion of the fillers inside the polymeric matrix was studied. Three different dispersion states, fiber, particle aggregates and clay, were formed in the composites because of the natural differences in the filler structures. The thermal and mechanical performance of the biocomposites was greatly influenced by these dispersion states. It was found that miscanthus fiber was the optimal filler to improve the stiffness of the blends among these three fillers. The MFI studies showed that all the composites possess low MFI values, which ensure their processability by casting/blown filming or thermoforming.

1 INTRODUCTION

Biobased and biodegradable polymeric materials provide a different outlook on sustainable development and circular economy from the conventional plastics used today. Bio-based plastics can reduce dependency on unsustainable fossil fuel feedstocks [1]. Biodegradable plastics will easily disintegrate and biodegrade into CO₂, water and biomass when disposed of in the environment [2], reducing plastic pollution. To expand the applications of bioplastics, polymers normally need to be modified, especially in terms of mechanical properties, to fit different needs.

As an emerging area in polymer science, polymer composites show their advantages through special properties and cost-competitiveness. Blending of biodegradable plastics with compostable biomass fillers, such as natural fiber, agricultural residues and mineral fillers, has attracted a wide range of interests in the scientific and industrial world. The filler type, size, and the interaction between the filler and polymeric matrix have been researched for their importance in determining the final properties of the biocomposites. In our group's previous research, it was found that the agricultural-residues and perennial grasses can be used as value additives to biodegradable plastics [3-5]. Nagarajan et al.'s study showed that the source of the biomass filler would influence the final properties of the composites [3]. Simonet et al.'s research found that the plasticization of the biomass filler was beneficial for the processing and properties of this kind of biocomposite [6]. Unfortunately, high loading contents of the biomass filler resulted in a dramatic decline in the mechanical properties of the composites, especially the toughness. How to fabricate a high toughness biocomposite with high loading content of biomass filler has been a long-term challenge in the biodegradable polymer field. In this work, resulting from the use of a super-toughened polymer blend as the polymer matrix, large contents of biomass filler were introduced and finally biocomposites with high impact strength were successfully fabricated.

A lot of research has been conducted to explore the methods to modify the mechanical properties of polymers. Among them, melt blending of two or more polymers with different properties has been certified to be an effective method to engineer a mechanical balance of alloys [7]. However, poor compatibility between different polymers is a natural defect in polymer blends, because of the different surface tensions. To improve the compatibility, in-situ reactive extrusion or ex-situ compatibilization has been extensively studied in the melt blending process. In-situ reactive extrusion has been widely applied in industrial processes due to its versatility and economic benefit [8].

In this research, a highly compatibilized biodegradable blend, with one phase dispersed in nano-scale, was successfully prepared via reactive extrusion [9], and was used as a matrix for blending with different fillers. Sustainable biocomposites with high loadings of filler contents were fabricated, and their properties-structure relationship was evaluated in this research.

2. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTS

Biodegradable PBS (Th803s) and PBAT (Th801t) were purchased from Xinjiang Blueridge Tunhe Chemical Industry Co. Ltd, China. Luperox 101, used as a peroxide, was obtained from Sigma-Aldrich, Canada and was used as received. High aspect ratio talc (HAR[®] T84) with average particle size of 2 μm from Imerys (Imerys Performance Additives Division, Canada), miscanthus fiber with average length of 2 mm and oat hull with fiber length of 1 cm and harvested in southern Ontario, Canada, and used for fabricating the biocomposites.

The nano-blends of PBS/PBAT (80/20) were prepared via reactive extrusion in the presence of peroxide (0.02 phr) in a twin-screw extruder (Leistritz Micro-27, Germany) at 175 °C and 100 rpm. The extruded nano-blends were used as the matrix for various fillers which were introduced into the blends and injected into samples for characterization using a micro DSM Explore (DSM, Netherlands) system. The nano-blends were labeled as HIPBS in this research and 20 wt% talc, miscanthus fiber, or oat hull were introduced into the HIPBS separately to fabricate the biocomposites. The nomenclature and composition of the samples prepared in this work are shown in table 1.

Table 1: The composition ratio of the biocomposites.

Sample	Percentage of HIPBS (wt%)	Percentage of filler (wt%)
HIPBS	100	0
HIPBS-20% Talc	80	20 Talc
HIPBS-20% Miscanthus Fiber	80	20 Miscanthus fiber
HIPBS-20% Oat Hull	80	20 Oat hull

The nano-dispersion morphology and dispersion of the fillers in the matrix were characterized by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) (JEOL JEM-1200 Ex II) at a voltage of 80 kV, and Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) (Multimode 8, Bruker Nano Inc., CA, U.S.A.) with peak force tapping model technology. According to ASTM D638, the tensile properties of the nano-blend and its composites were characterized by Instron universal testing systems. The strain rate is 50 mm/min. In accordance with ASTM D256, notched impact samples were tested using an impact testing instrument (Testing Machine Inc. US). 5 specimens were tested for each sample.

The melt flow index (MFI) of the composites were tested based on ASTM D1238 at 210 °C with a weight of 7.16 kg. Three tests were repeated to obtain the average MFI values. The crystallization properties of the composites were tested by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) technology (TA Q200, US), and the samples were heated from room temperature to 200 °C, cooled down to 30 °C, and then heated again up to 200 °C, both the heating and cooling speed are 10 °C/min.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1: Microscopy Images of (A) TEM image of HIPBS (PBS80/PBAT20/Peroxide 0.02 phr) nano-blend; (B) AFM image of HIPBS nano-blend (scale of the AFM image is $2 \times 2 \mu\text{m}$).

Figure 2: The mechanical performance of the nano-blends and their composites: (A) tensile modulus and (B) notched impact strength. Sample: a – nano-blend matrix, b – 20% oat hull, c – 20% miscanthus fiber, and d – 20% talc.

The nano-dispersion of the PBAT in PBS were certified by the microscopy images in Fig. 1. Fig. 1A shows the TEM images of the prepared PBS/PBAT blends with the PBAT dispersed in the PBS matrix at a nano-scale of $\sim 100 \text{ nm}$. The nano-dispersed PBAT in PBS can be easily distinguished in the AFM images shown in Fig. 1B. The low modulus PBAT is indicated by the darker, brown color in the AFM modulus tapping mode, surrounded by the high modulus PBS which is shown as a golden-yellow color. Due to nano-structures formed in the blends, the resulted material exhibited super-toughness and high melt strength [10].

Fig. 2. shows the mechanical properties of the composites and the matrix blends. The stiffness is demonstrated by tensile modulus in Fig. 2A and the toughness is shown by notched impact strength in Fig. 2B. The addition of the fillers significantly increased the modulus of the blends, especially with the incorporation of talc and miscanthus fiber, which showed a 3-fold increase. Due to the super toughness of the matrix, the composites with 20% filler still showed high toughness, with impact strengths of $\sim 170 \text{ J/m}$ (hinge break) and high elongation at break of $\sim 33\%$. The mechanical performance of the biocomposites is comparable to the conventional petrol-based plastic,

polypropylene [11]. The stiffness-toughness balance performance ensured the potential for a large range of applications for these biocomposites.

Table 2: The effects of the filler on the melt flow index of the composites.

Samples	Melt flow index (210 °C, 2.16 kg)
HIPBS	0.16
HIPBS-20% Talc	< 0.1
HIPBS-20% Miscanthus Fiber	9.48
HIPBS-20% Oat Hull	11.40

The melt flow index (MFI) of the biocomposites is shown in Table 2. It was found that the MFI of the polymeric matrix increased with the addition of the biomass fillers, miscanthus fiber and oat hull. This may be due to the high temperature degradation of the biomass fillers. However, the increased MFI indicated that the flow processability of the materials has been improved. In contrast, the addition of talc decreased the MFI because of its filler effects. The chain movement in the blend was limited in the presence of the talc filler. The MFI of all composites was lower than 15 g/10 min, indicating that the bio-composites can be used for melt processing, such as casting film and thermoforming.

Figure 3: The DSC curves of the biocomposites: (A) cooling curves at 10 °C/min; (B) heating curves at 10 °C/min.

The effect of the fillers on the crystallization of the HIPBS is shown in Fig. 3. Because of the high compatibility between the PBS and PBAT, only one crystallization peak and melting peak was found for the HIPBS. The introduction of filler did not influence the crystallization and melting temperatures of the polymeric matrix. The crystallinity calculated from the 2nd heating curves also showed that the crystallinity of the HIPBS was not influenced by any of the fillers. The unchanged crystallinity indicated that the increased stiffness of the composites was due to the enhancement effect of the fillers, but not changes to the polymeric matrix itself. The low melting point (~114 °C) endowed the biocomposites with good processability at low temperature, e.g. ~180 °C, without decomposition of the biomass fillers at high temperatures.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The stiffness-toughness balance of biocomposites with a high loading of filler content (20 wt%) was successfully achieved in this research via the design of the nano-blend matrix. Due to the improved compatibility by reactive extrusion, the PBAT dispersed into PBS at a nano-scale which resulted in a super-toughened biodegradable matrix. Different kinds of fillers, including miscanthus

fiber, oat hull and talc, were introduced into the matrix by melt compounding. The super-toughness of the biodegradable matrix resulted in the processed biocomposites possessing high toughness with impact strengths greater than 150 J/m. The introduction of fillers greatly improved the stiffness of the matrix with increased tensile modulus from 470 MPa to 1250 MPa. It was found that the uniform dispersed filler greatly increased the modulus of the blends, without the loss of high toughness. The crystallinity studies showed that the crystallinity of the matrix, HIPBS, was not influenced by the fillers, indicating that the fillers cannot be worked as nucleation agents for the HIPBS. Conversely, the unchanged crystallinity also indicated that the improved stiffness was ascribed to the filler enhancement effects, instead of changes in crystallinity of the polymeric matrix. The high biomass loaded biocomposites are expected to have great potential in packaging and daily commodity products with cost-competitiveness to current non-biodegradable plastics.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank the following for their financial support to carry out this research: (1) the Ontario Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Rural Affairs (OMAFRA)/University of Guelph – Bioeconomy for Industrial Uses Research Program (Project # 030054) and the OMAFRA/University of Guelph Product Development and Enhancement through Value Chains Theme (Project # 030146); (2) the Agriculture and Agri-Food Canada (AAFC) and Competitive Green Technologies through AgriInnovation Program project (Project # 052882 and 051910); and (3) the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council (NSERC), Canada Discovery Grants (Project # 401111 and 400320).

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